

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF FOREIGN ACCENT ON PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION: EMPIRICAL RESEARCH

Kolesnikova A.,

PhD, Associate Professor

Department of Linguistics, Translation and Intercultural Communication

Faculty of Foreign Languages and Area Studies

Lomonosov Moscow State University

Moscow, Russia

Frolova V.

Student

Department of Linguistics, Translation and Intercultural Communication

Faculty of Foreign Languages and Area Studies

Lomonosov Moscow State University

Moscow, Russia

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Abstract

The literature review over the past 20 years indicates a particular interest towards foreign accent perception in business environment and reveals biased attitude of natives, whether employers or employees, to non-nativeness in terms of phonological competence in the studied field. While the attitude of natives has been thoroughly researched, immigrants' opinions might vary and require careful consideration. This study aims to examine to which extent, if any, a foreign accent in the German language affects professional communication of Russian-speaking immigrants living and working in Germany (in fields including IT, finance, healthcare, education, etc.). In total, 108 participants aged 22-62 completed a questionnaire, the primary purpose of which was to explore whether a foreign accent is perceived as a hindrance in business environment. The research included a quantitative analysis of gathered statistical information processed via JASP software, as well as a qualitative analysis of open-ended items. The major finding indicates that for 39.8% of the participants, a foreign accent has no influence on interactions within a business context. According to the results of the questionnaire, 31.5% of the respondents have never found themselves confronted with a problem of not being understood due to a foreign accent. Finally, for more than a half of the surveyed participants, namely 53.7%, their foreign accent had no bearing on the accomplishment of job-related tasks as part of the working process whatsoever.

Keywords: foreign accent, second language, accentism, German linguoculture, workplace, professional discourse

Introduction

Throughout the first quarter of the 21st century, society has witnessed a rapid spread of oral intercultural communication. However, if a person's speech contains phonological features that point towards non-nativeness and make an utterance unintelligible, it reduces a native speaker's interest in the act of communication [1]. Not only can a foreign accent make an utterance difficult to understand and make a native speaker unwilling to communicate further, but also its presence can lead to an unconscious negative evaluation of the speaker [7]. According to U. Hirschfeld, a German phonetician, despite the fact that a foreign accent is an unavoidable feature of non-natives' speech, a non-native speaker with a less pronounced accent will be better evaluated by native listeners not only in terms of their language proficiency, but also in terms of their education, social background and personality traits [7].

Researchers' statements above show that, to this day, an accent is a variable that has a significant effect both on the success of communication and on the perception of an interlocutor's background. As the current study targeted Russian immigrants living and working

in Germany, it appears relevant to evaluate the perception of their accent by interlocutors. One of the prior studies researched the impact of Russian immigrants' foreign accent on integration prospects within the German community, showing that in certain cases it can directly influence the prospect of one's integration into a new foreign language environment – a process that could also be connected to how well a person will fare in their professional endeavours [2].

As Germany is known to be home to a large number of Russian immigrants, one of the studies focused on the question whether Russian-speaking immigrants in Germany (various social environments) are discriminated against because of a foreign accent. To this end, the survey targeted 145 Russian-speaking immigrants who were 18-65 years of age and lived in ten of Germany's federal states (Berlin, Bavaria, North Rhine-Westphalia, Hamburg, Baden-Württemberg etc.) According to the results, over half of the informants (53%) had experienced discrimination due to a foreign accent. Based on their findings, the researchers concluded that an immigrant's successful integration into the German community necessitates acquisition of phonological

competence in a target language to prevent discriminatory attitudes as well as misunderstandings and breakdowns in communication due to poor speech intelligibility [2].

The above research established that the number of Russian immigrants who had at least once faced accent-based discrimination in Germany prevailed. This and all of the aforementioned indicates the relevance of the current study, which also researched potential instances of accent discrimination faced by Russian-speaking immigrants living and working in Germany albeit with special emphasis laid on workplace context. The overarching research aim was to explore whether a foreign accent is perceived as a hindrance in business environment. Ultimately, the findings indicate a positive shift towards natives' perception of accented speech, when it comes to a German community.

Accent perception in business environment

Among other things, transition from written to oral discourse in the 21st century pertains to business contexts. Apropos professional discourse, when people from different L1 and cultural backgrounds communicate to solve certain job-related tasks, their foreign accents might impede communication process. It is, therefore, of particular interest to assess the communicative effect of a foreign accent in this regard.

The effect of a foreign accent has been thoroughly researched. One of the studies exploring the issue was based on a quantitative analysis of the data collected by means of a survey. The informants were 40-45 years of age, predominantly from the UK, while the rest came from Germany, France and the USA. 87.25% of the informants acknowledged the impact of a foreign accent on communication in business environment. At the same time, 81.25% of the respondents deemed this influence to be insignificant and only 6.25% reported that an accent had a significant impact on the success of professional communication. Most of the informants (81.25%) claimed they always understood their clients, business partners or non-native speakers in business context [3].

At the same time, there are many descriptions of the "distractive impact" of a foreign accent on professional communication [10]. Researchers in the field are acutely aware of this impact, and concerns are voiced that "a foreign accent interferes with successful business communication" [11]. In this regard the concept of accentism should not be overlooked. Sometimes it is not just unintelligible speech that is the reason for mistreatment at the workplace, but the sole fact of having a foreign accent. Accentism is thus recognised as a type of "linguistic bias in which inequitable treatment is based on a speaker's accent". The effect of such a bias "may be particularly pronounced in business and professional settings", so employees risk feeling belittled due to having an accent [13].

For instance, in a survey among the EU member states, 34% of a representative sample of respondents claimed that during the hiring process, a candidate whose speech was less accented would be given preference as opposed to a candidate with the same credentials but with a foreign accent [6].

The research conducted in 2022 also exemplifies the accentism phenomenon. 96 English speakers from Calgary (Canada) were asked to evaluate the audio recordings of 12 English speakers (for 6 of them English was their L1, for the other 6 – L2, while the mother tongue of the latter was Tagalog, one of the main languages of the Philippines). The audio recordings were based on scenarios recreating situations in which job-related tasks needed to be solved in English. In this study, accentedness, performance level and job prestige were taken into account. As a result, the listeners rated native English speakers as more competent than native Tagalog speakers ($p < .001$, OR = 7.13, 95% CI [3.05, 16.68]). Among the latter, those speakers whose accent was weaker were rated as more competent than those whose accent was stronger ($p = .931$, OR = 1.14, 95% CI [0.65, 2.00]) [13].

One more study in the related field was conducted in 2020 in Canada. The research aim was to test whether physicians who have a foreign accent are perceived as less competent than physicians who speak with a standard Canadian accent. The doctor participating in the study delivered either good or bad news related to the patient's health condition. While there was detected an overall negative assessment of physicians' professionalism upon receiving disappointing news, the listeners still rated the expertise of a physician who spoke with a standard Canadian accent more highly. This indicates that a foreign accent can have a significant impact on patients' assessment of a doctor's competence, who risks facing prejudice and mistrust if their speech is accented [4].

Another research was carried out in 2018 at the request of the Chamber of Labour (Vienna, Austria) by SORA Institute for Social Research and Consulting via random sampling) in the form of a telephone interview. Out of a total of 2,317 respondents, 62% of all immigrants and 74% of all respondents with a noticeably different origin (e.g., skin colour, clothing or accent) considered that ethnicity (including a foreign accent) one of the main grounds for discrimination in Austria. The findings Compared to Austrians, migrants who speak German with a foreign accent are 1.5-2 times more likely to be discriminated against, which can be clearly seen in the professional context. One respondent (an immigrant from Hungary) described her experience in this respect as follows: "Being of Hungarian origin, I have been facing more and more discrimination in Austria in recent years, mainly when looking for a new job". Alongside the age, she highlighted a foreign accent as one of the reasons for discrimination [10].

If a person feels that an accent impedes professional communication and interferes with the accomplishment of one's duties, it may also lead to decreased satisfaction with one's occupation. In this connection, a study conducted on a sample of 256 foreign-born workers revealed the impact of perceived accent discrimination on immigrants' commitment to their jobs. 41.4% of the participants were Asian ($n = 106$), 24.6% – White ($n = 63$), 22.7% – Latino ($n = 58$), 1.2% – Black ($n = 3$), 10.2% – Other ($n = 26$). They had immigrated to the USA from 52 different countries (for instance, China, India, Turkey) and the period of living in the

USA was 1-70 years. The findings established negative relation of perceived accent discrimination to job satisfaction ($c1 = -.20$, $p < .05$) and affective commitment (a sample item for “affective commitment” was as follows: “I really feel as if my organization’s problems are my own.”) ($c2 = -.22$, $p < .01$) [8].

The review of literature in the studied field shows that despite positive findings (namely, a small number of workplace issues related to speech unintelligibility, according to [3]) revealed by some of the studies, non-native accent still remains a source of discriminatory attitudes that influence the hiring process, communication in business environment and motivation to fulfil job-related duties.

Research questions

Based on the review of the prior findings in the field, the impact of a foreign accent on business communication does not seem clear-cut. With a relatively high number of instances related to accent discrimination at the workplace one cannot fully acknowledge that a thoroughly positive shift in natives’ attitudes towards accented speech is underway, hence the relevance of the current study.

The research questions are as follows:

RQ1. Do you think you have a foreign accent when you speak German?

RQ2. How strong do you think your accent is (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “a very strong accent” and 7 is “no accent”)?

RQ3. Have you received any comments about your foreign accent in German at the workplace (from colleagues/your boss) (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “constantly” and 7 is “never”)?

RQ4. Please specify what comments you have received.

RQ5. Does foreign accent affect your interaction with others in a professional environment (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “significantly” and 7 is “does not affect at all”)?

RQ6. Throughout your career, have you ever found yourself in a situation when your colleagues, your boss or customers found your speech unintelligible (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “constantly” and 7 is “never”)?

RQ7. Please provide an example.

RQ8. Does your foreign accent interfere with your professional tasks? If yes, to what extent? (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “very seriously interferes” and 7 is “does not interfere at all”)

RQ9. If you have had difficulty accomplishing a professional task due to a foreign accent, please give an example.

Methodology

The study itself is an Internet-based survey. This type was mainly opted for due to a reduced amount of time taken “to distribute and gather data that could then be processed automatically” [5]. In addition to this, Internet-based surveys “can yield representative data as they can reach a wider audience” and ensure “anonymity, honesty and authenticity: as the participants’ responses are “anonymous and not face-to-face” [5].

The survey was comprised of dichotomous and multiple-choice questions used for “General information” section as well as questions based on a 7-point Likert scale for “Research questions” section. This rating scale is known for “the greater subtlety of response which $<...>$ renders this a very attractive and widely used instrument in research”. One of its major advantages is “a degree of sensitivity and differentiation of response” alongside generating numbers for further statistical analysis (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018, p. 480). The number of scale points (seven) was chosen on purpose to ensure reliability (“Reliability is higher when you have more scale points”, “seven-point scales seem to be preferable in terms of reliability” and “the ability of respondents to discriminate between the values in the scales”) [5].

Besides rating scales, the questionnaire contained open-ended questions aimed at collecting more detailed information on the subject and ensuring research validity and reliability (“Open-ended items often provide more valid and reliable responses than closed items”) [9].

The participants of this study were 108 Russian-speaking immigrants (median age = 39.5, minimum age = 22, maximum age = 62) currently living and working in Germany in various fields ranging from IT, finance, sales, supply chain to law, healthcare, education, etc. They were administered an anonymous online questionnaire (see Appendix A).

To guarantee confidentiality of identity and to observe ethical standards, the respondents were not required to submit identification details and were asked for their consent to the submitted data processing at the beginning of the survey.

The items in the questionnaire matched the research questions of the study and also included a “General information” section containing questions about the respondents’ age, gender, language proficiency and occupation. The main aim of the questionnaire was to find out if a foreign accent has a bearing on one’s career, namely the career of Russian-speaking immigrants in Germany.

Results

Data analysis was carried out via JASP [14]: the participants’ answers were submitted into the software in order to get descriptive statistical information. Integer values (1 to 7) were designated for each label of scale points in accordance with the Likert scale standards. Descriptive statistics for collected data can be seen below in tables 1-5.

RQ1. Do you think you have a foreign accent when you speak German?

The majority of the respondents ($n=92$, 85.2%) gave a positive answer and believe they do have an accent, while 7.4% of the answers ($n=8$) equally account for negative or “not sure” responses.

RQ2. How strong do you think your accent is (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “a very strong accent” and 7 is “no accent”)?

For Question 2, the largest share of participants settled for “a moderate accent” ($n=27$, 25%, $M(\text{median})=4$). At the same time, the next most popular response was “the accent is quite distinct” ($n=25$, 23.1%).

Only 5.5% equally (n=6) associated the strength of their accent with the extremes of the scale – “a very strong accent” and “no accent”.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of the Gathered Data for RQ2.

Descriptive statistics			
Valid	108	Skewness	0.016
Missing	0	Std. Error of Skewness	0.233
Mean	4.037	Kurtosis	-0.594
Median	4.000	Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.461
Mode	4	Minimum	1
Std. Deviation	1.527	Maximum	7

Figure 1
Responses to RQ2

RQ3. Have you received any comments about your foreign accent in German at the workplace (from colleagues/your boss) (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “constantly” and 7 is “never”)?

never” receiving such comments (M=6, n=37, 34.2%), which was the most frequently chosen response. These findings indicate that accent tends to be taken out of the equation when communicating with non-natives in a business context. None of the respondents chose the “very often” option, and only 2 participants (0.9%) admitted their foreign accent was “constantly” commented on.

For Question 3, there was registered a clear tendency towards not receiving any comments about one’s foreign accent whatsoever (n=34, 31.5%) or “almost

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of the Gathered Data for RQ3.

Descriptive statistics			
Valid	108	Skewness	-1.035
Missing	0	Std. Error of Skewness	0.233
Mean	5.620	Kurtosis	0.695
Median	6.000	Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.461
Mode	6	Minimum	1
Std. Deviation	1.379	Maximum	7

Figure 2
Responses to RQ3

RQ4. Please specify what comments you have received.

Of the number of 108 respondents, 62% chose to elaborate on the topic, and there were in total 14 comments (21%) containing positive feedback on the participants' accent. Among the comments were: "*charming accent*", "*I received only positive comments. Sometimes my boss can correct the pronunciation if the stress is wrongly placed, but she does it with tolerance and respect. Never got any comments about the accent from other colleagues.*"

Quite often the participants mentioned questions about the country of origin ($n=23$, 34%) which they received due to their foreign accent: "*Where do you come from?*", "*Where are you from? You speak perfect German, but I can hear an accent in your speech. France, Poland, Russia, Sweden?*" This illustrates the point that accent tends to be associated with one's background and nationality.

Only 5 of the provided comments (7.5%) were judgemental, along the lines of the following: "*You have lived six years in Germany by now. Why haven't you learned to speak German better?*"

RQ5. Does foreign accent affect your interaction with others in a professional environment (from 1 to 7, where 1 is "significantly" and 7 is "does not affect at all")?

The following question indicates an increasingly positive trend with regard to the research topic, as, according to 39.8% of the participants, foreign accent has no bearing on their interactions within a workplace context ($n=43$). Still, ca. 60% of the respondents ($n=65$) acknowledged the impact of foreign accent on business communication. 24 of all the respondents ($M=6$, 22.2%) claimed their foreign accent "hardly" affects professional communication. Only 1 respondent (0.9%) reported a significant influence of their foreign accent in this respect.

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics of the Gathered Data for RQ5.

Descriptive statistics			
Valid	108	Skewness	-0.886
Missing	0	Std. Error of Skewness	0.233
Mean	5.574	Kurtosis	-0.253
Median	6.000	Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.461
Mode	7	Minimum	1
Std. Deviation	1.559	Maximum	7

Figure 3
Responses to RQ5

RQ6. Throughout your career, have you ever found yourself in a situation when your colleagues, your boss or customers found your speech unintelligible (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “constantly” and 7 is “never”)?

findings, the issue of unintelligible speech is not widely spread in German workplace context, with most of the participants answering they either have “almost never” (M=6, n=38, 35.2%) or “never” (n=34, 31.5%) faced a situation when their speech was found unintelligible.

For Question 6, none of the respondents chose the “constantly” or “very often” option. According to the

Table 4

Descriptive Statistics of the Gathered Data for RQ6.

Descriptive statistics			
Valid	108	Skewness	-0.762
Missing	0	Std. Error of Skewness	0.233
Mean	5.833	Kurtosis	0.018
Median	6.000	Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.461
Mode	6	Minimum	3
Std. Deviation	1.067	Maximum	7

Figure 4
Responses to RQ6

RQ7. If yes, please provide an example.

Of all the participants, 32 participants exemplified their responses, mostly highlighting the fact they were asked to repeat certain words or sentences (n=11, 34.4%). Among the submitted answers were the following ones:

“The inaccurate pronunciation of sounds resulted in a change of meaning, which led to misunderstandings”.

“One of my patients aid she could not understand what I was saying even after repeating the sentence twice”.

“I sometimes find that people listen to me in a different way when I speak, they come closer and pay attention to my articulation.”

“It’s mostly about speech tempo, not pronunciation. I work in an international team dominated by Germans. The accent is irrelevant as long as I speak correctly and quickly enough.”

RQ8. Does your foreign accent interfere with your professional tasks? If yes, to what extent (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “very seriously interferes” and 7 is “does not interfere at all”)?

As for the completion of job-related tasks, for more than a half of the participants, their foreign accent does not interfere with the process at all (M=7, n=58, 53.7%), and for 23 respondents (21%), the accent “mostly does not interfere”, which points towards the fact that accent is not predominatly perceived as a hindrance in a workplace context.

Table 5

Descriptive Statistics of the Gathered Data for RQ8.

Descriptive statistics			
Valid	108	Skewness	-1.656
Missing	0	Std. Error of Skewness	0.233
Mean	6.129	Kurtosis	3.019
Median	7.000	Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.461
Mode	7	Minimum	1
Std. Deviation	1.203	Maximum	7

Figure 5
Responses to RQ8

RQ9. If you have had difficulty accomplishing a professional task due to a foreign accent, please give an example.

Of the total number of participants, 24 (22.2%) provided a more detailed description of their experience, leaving the following comments in the survey:

“Giving speeches or participating in debates was sometimes made more difficult because of an accent.”

“Generally, foreign accent is an obstacle to climbing the career ladder.”

“Human factor is always out there. In most cases, treatment of an “outsider” is different from that of an in-group member.”

Discussion, Limitations and Recommendations for Further Research

The ultimate findings indicate that 39.8% of the respondents do not experience the impact of a foreign accent on professional communication, and accented speech interferes with the accomplishment of job-related tasks only slightly (for 53.7% their accent is no

hindrance at all). Coming back to the reviewed literature, it can be stated that the impact of foreign accent on business interactions is gradually diminishing and is seeing a positive change in general. Still, the presence of negative treatment at the workplace cannot be denied, which necessitates further exploration of accentism and accent-based discrimination cases.

An agenda for future surveys related to the topic sets out a number of limitations of the current research and possible recommendations. To fully reflect the general trend, the number of respondents could be widened (a wider scope of respondents from other German-speaking countries or other cultures could be looked at). Further questionnaire could concentrate on the impact of a foreign accent on the success in certain career fields.

Conclusions

The main conclusion drawn from the research is that the impact of a foreign accent on the success of professional communication is not so profound as to completely prevent the accomplishment of one's professional duties (31.5% reported not receiving any comments about one's foreign accent at all (n=34)).

According to the received data, within a business context, foreign accent influences professional communication for ca. 60% of the participants, whereas ca. 40% claim not to experience this impact. Moreover, for Russian-speaking immigrants, the issue of speech unintelligibility proved not so widespread in the German business context, with 35.2% and 31.5% of the participants respectively answering they have "almost never" or "never" found themselves in a situation when their speech was found unintelligible. **For more than a half of the participants, their foreign accent had no bearing on the working process whatsoever.**

To summarise, the findings of the study have established the influence of a foreign accent on communication in a business setting and pointed up a positive trend regarding attitudes towards accented speech of non-natives at the workplace. **If respect and tolerance towards non-natives' accented speech is fostered at the workplace, the situation has yet to improve even further.**

Appendix A

Questionnaire administered to the participants

I have been informed that participation in the survey is anonymous and I agree to the processing of submitted data.

Yes

General information

1. Please state your age:

2. Please state your gender:

Male

Female

3. Did you take a German language test when you moved to Germany?

Yes

No

4. If you took an examination when you moved to Germany, please state the level in accordance with the language test result:

A1

A2

B1

B2

C1

C2

5. What is the career field in which you are currently employed?

6. Please specify the length of service in this career field.

Research questions

1. Do you think you have a foreign accent when you speak German?

Yes

No

Not sure

2. How strong do you think your accent is (from 1 to 7, where 1 is "a very strong accent" and 7 is "no accent")?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
A very strong accent	A strong accent	The accent is quite distinct	A moderate accent	A slight accent	Almost no accent	No accent

3. Have you received any comments about your foreign accent in German at the workplace (from colleagues/your boss) (from 1 to 7, where 1 is "constantly" and 7 is "never")?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Constantly	Very often	Often	Occasionally	Rarely	Almost never	Never

4. Please specify what comments you have received.

5. Does foreign accent affect your interaction with others in a professional environment (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “significantly” and 7 is “does not affect at all”)?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Significantly	Very much	Moderately	To some extent	Insignificantly	Hardly	Does not affect at all

6. Throughout your career, have you ever found yourself in a situation when your colleagues, your boss or customers found your speech unintelligible (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “constantly” and 7 is “never”)?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Constantly	Very often	Quite often	Occasionally	Sometimes	Almost never	Never

7. Please provide an example.

8. Does your foreign accent interfere with your professional tasks? If yes, to what extent (from 1 to 7, where 1 is “very seriously interferes” and 7 is “does not interfere at all”)?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Very seriously interferes	Mostly interferes	More likely than not	Not sure	Does not interfere in general	Mostly does not interfere	Does not interfere at all

9. If you have had difficulty accomplishing a professional task due to a foreign accent, please give an example.

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